

Detection and measurement of double stars (L. Lindgren 78-03-10)1. How many new double stars will be discovered by the satellite?

In an observing program with 50000 stars (systems) there will be about 35000 non-single systems (nss). I estimate that these will be distributed according to detectability etc as shown in the table below.

	previously known nss	previously not known nss	total
detected by satellite	4550	1758	6308
not detected by satellite	1213	27479	28692
total	5763	29237	35000

These estimates are based on the following three assumptions.

A. The separation ρ and magnitude difference Δm of the secondary are distributed according to eq. (1) in my note 78-02-01, with $R_0 = 0".5$.

B. The satellite detects a nss if and only if $\rho_{\min}(\Delta m) < \rho \leq 15''$, where $\rho_{\min}(\Delta m)$ is given below as function of Δm .

Δm	0.25	0.75	1.25	1.75	2.25	2.75	3.25	>3.5
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$\rho_{\min}(\Delta m)$	0".11	0.12	0.14	0.16	0.20	0.26	0.45	∞
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$\rho_{\min}(\Delta m)$ is roughly 1.1 times the minimum projected separation for detection, $d_{\min}$, given in Table 2 of the note 78-02-01.

C. Present double-star catalogues contain all nss with $\rho_1(\Delta m) < \rho \leq 15''$, one half of the nss with $\rho_0(\Delta m) < \rho \leq \rho_1(\Delta m)$, and none with $\rho \leq \rho_0(\Delta m)$. Here, $\lg \rho_0 = 0.22\Delta m - 1.0$ and $\lg \rho_1 = 0.22\Delta m - 0.5$. These completeness factors, due to Heintz (1969), are probably slightly optimistic in our case since they are used by Heintz only for $V < 9.0$ and $\delta > -30^\circ$. Thus, the number of new nss (1758) might be underestimated.

2. Precision of double stars measures

Figs. 1 - 2 show the mean errors σ_d and $\sigma_{\Delta m}$ of the projected separation d and magnitude difference Δm , as functions of d and Δm . The m.e. are computed for a 4^s observation of a $B = 9^m$ star with the baseline instrument described in the note 7802-01. From the accumulated observations of a given system it should certainly be possible to improve $\sigma_{\Delta m}$ considerably. It has not been studied how (and if) the true separation ρ and position angle θ can be derived from measured projected distances; thus σ_d only gives a rough indication of σ_ρ .

Fig. 1

Fig. 2